

Mathematical Modelling Approach to Enhance Employability Skills for Graduating Class in Dakshina Kannada(DK) District.

Employability of graduating class students under existing macroeconomic situations indicated that there was a communication gap in certain regions where the student's mother tongue was not scheduled in the constitution. In this descriptive research, the authors try to describe a phenomenon and attempt to build/improve on it, i.e the gap discovered and come out with a model that can solve employability problems(i.e. Communication skills, interpersonal skills, reasoning skills etc.) related to the SANKALP scheme.(under the Minister of State for Skill Development and Entrepreneurship)

Key Words: Employability, Dakshina Kannada(DK),SANKALP scheme,

1. Introduction.

Skill Acquisition and Knowledge Awareness for Livelihood Promotion (“SANKALP”) scheme, a programme initiated by the Ministry of Skill Development along with a loan from World bank, aimed at improving livelihood through short term development of skills thereby strengthening institutions and bringing inclusion of marginalized sections of the society with increased market connectivity. The three key result areas measured in this joint project, which lays the foundation of vision document for 2047 by Government of India(GOI) were i) Institutional Strengthening at Central, State and District level ii) Quality assurance of skill development programmes and iii) Inclusion of marginalized population in skill development programmes. These areas were measured by around 8 disbursement linked indicators(DLIs)across these three areas by executing multiple projects. Karnataka’s SANKALP role is in primarily developing and building capacity at national level through some of her renowned private and state universities apart from institutes of national importance and eminence present geographically in the state. NAAC accredited Colleges and deemed to be universities aligned their graduating class students at all levels(Vocational, graduate and post graduates) with this particular mission of government(both at district and state level) thereby developing institutional strengthening

as well as inclusion of marginalized sections of society at both district and state levels within Karnataka and hence trying to continue on with Karnataka's SANKALP for a better and prosperous nation as a whole.

2. Literature Review

A key aspect in analyzing the quality of university provision is employability. Responsibility of employability lies in four key stakeholders, students, higher education institutions, employers and government. Thus, to meet the regular vocational skill challenges by both employers as well as those set up according to the government agenda, employability is a key concept that has to be understood by institutes of higher education. In this section, review of employability as well as employment both from micro and macro economic situations that arise are discussed thereby giving opportunities for institutes of higher education to excel in providing quality education. Martins et al. (2020, p. 289) remarks that soft skills can serve two functions, employability and professional success during a crisis that has to be acquired in higher education.

For an uncertain future, which includes "potentially cataclysmic events such as extreme climate events, terrorism and pandemics" (Martins et al., 2020, p. 280), students need to be equipped with a specific set of soft skills and hence the authors conceptualized a three-tiered model: the "foundation component" with knowledge, skills and attitudes, the "transversal cognitive and meta-cognitive component" and the "social and emotional component" (Martins et al., 2020, p. 288). Though, the authors are not clear whether soft skills can make students cope with uncertainty and hence should this new set of skills alongside 21st century skills be taught because of the existence of teaching infrastructure and access to the millennial generation. For this, in this study we created a modified conceptual structure that consisted of two exclusive different sets of social and emotional/affective components than a single one as per Martins et al.

3. Setup of Experimental Career(/Placement) Research.

Skill development opportunities for all sections, inability to resolve youth aspirations,

mobilization and retention of trainees mainly women and disadvantaged groups, demand articulation of MSMEs are some of the challenges that SANKALP has been facing since its inception in 2019.

In this study, which is more descriptive and experimental, for the first five to six weeks of the study, thoughtful and supportive exercises like multiple types of group discussion along with various methods of personal interviewing were included in pre campus recruitment process and participant's progress were studied as a part of Srinivas University's unique stage wise campus placement conditioning process for its eligible students who have crossed either one or some of the following stages.

Stage 1 : Campus Earn While You Learn Program

Stage 2 : Arrange Part-Time or Temporary Work Placements at Campus

Stage 3 : Arrange assigning Freelance and Consulting Gig Campus Placements

Stage 4 : Facilitate Projects and Internship Placements

Stage 5 : Continuous Career Counseling, Mentoring & Training

Stage 6 : Final Campus Recruitment Interview Process

Stage 7 : Arrange Incubation Support for Entrepreneurial Ventures or Further Studies

Stage 8 : Career Networking Events and Recruitment Fairs

As a second step, the "Energy conservation Problem" together with "Food wastage Problem" were developed and discussed side by side in the study involving students and hotel management teachers as well as integrating S.T.E.M in the circular economy. This along with appropriate group discussion topics in innovation, relationship management etc. that provide aspiring students an opportunity to be employable and get suitable roles in banks, manufacturers, retail chains, food and hospitality industry etc.

Finally, in the third stage, the team made observations and inferences during the application of the problem and reported in which modeling indicators were derived. The modeling indicators for employability included communication(both verbal and non-verbal),listening skills, writing, presentation and public speaking, reasoning, leadership, interpersonal and time management skills.

Thus this research provides the description of modeling indicators along with the type of students for the graduating class of Srinivas University who were ready as well as employable and were well in alignment with Karnaaka SANKALP as well as SANKALP at national level.

4. Methodology

In this study, mathematical modeling methods were created to solve the real world SANKALP problems that have been encountered so far and that may occur in the future. The model includes not only mathematical structures of the model but also estimates, assumptions, estimates and strategies for solutions that apart from being mathematically correct, should be meaningful and adaptable for real life.

This model addresses key questions like employability solutions towards Karnataka SANKALP and SANKALP problems. Some of the key research questions that were addressed in this study were

- 1) How to infuse quality ?
- 2) How to increase the percentage of graduates who are either self employed/contract based employment to full time employment?
- 3) How to expand skills by developing PPP based startups?

By addressing the above questions, in a mathematical formulation relevant to the problem with suitable assumptions, this study tried to convert the real problem into a mathematical one, which is iterative and finally provide meaningful discussions and reflections on the mathematical results obtained. The modeling method is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Mathematical Modelling Approach

Finally, the study focused on providing solutions faced by SANKALP thereby putting forth a recommendation for the ministry of skill development and entrepreneurship for extension of the program for next two years until 2026 by not only giving a livelihood to certain sections but also strengthening the capacity of managers for companies who may also need the above workforce.

For this, we studied graduating class students in line with Srinivas university requirements, which was also well in alignment with Karnataka SANKALP, assuming that the current graduating batch will accomplish better both in taking care of their families as well as managing their livelihood in management is more effective and efficient than the earlier batches.

5. Discussion

A conceptual framework using four Venn diagrams has been proposed, primarily theoretical, to integrate STEM for better employability among Srinivas University students. This has been developed primarily keeping programs like UNNAT Bharat Abhyan, SANKALP as well as problems faced by authorities and officials for sustenance or extension. The four circles represents cognitive aspects, effective aspects, teaching/training aspects and social aspects that are basic for employability of Students by

Srinivas University educators, be it for their respective careers or livelihood as implied in schemes like Karnataka SANKALP/SANKALP.

Figure 2: Conceptual framework for employability

The different circles represented in the VENN diagram are

(A) Cognitive Aspects

{ Awareness of Knowledge,
Awareness of process,
Awareness of skills
Awareness of strategies}

(B) Social Aspects

{ Student,
Teachers,

Media,

Internal and External Organization}

(C) Affective Aspects

{ Perception of Job/Career Growth

Perception of Self/Family Requirements

Perception of Environment

Perception of Sustenance }

(D) Teaching/Training Aspects

{ Pedagogical knowledge,

Training Process,

Training skills,

Training strategies for career}

The intersection of the 4 circles in Venn Diagram give the following interesting findings that may be of use for solving SANKALP problems

1 $\{A \cap B\}$ = STEM Integration for execution

2 $\{B \cap C\}$ = Preserving STEM culture

3 $\{C \cap D\}$ = Inculcating STEM Thought

4 $\{A \cap D\}$ = Development of STEM Training

5 $\{A \cap B \cap C\}$ = Preserving STEM culture and integration

6 $\{A \cap D \cap C\}$ = Developing of STEM Training and Coaching Leadership

7 $\{A \cap B \cap C \cap D\}$ =Holistic Development

As of now, the above areas provided the researchers to categorize the students into the following types based on their employability skills. There were six modeling indicators for employability which were derived after scrutinizing the students as a result of our research. The scrutiny included the following 3 to 5 key steps and procedures.

- 1) General knowledge (assessed through objective tests including analytical aptitude for 25 marks, 15 minutes duration)
- 2) Group participation, Understanding of context situation and focusing on goals, formulating ideas and developing as well as taking initiative and reaching consensus were assessed through series of group discussion (3 rounds, in some cases 4 rounds) and finally
- 3) Personal interview (structured in STEM thinking for a particular job description) to finally identify employable students with quality and leadership with a panel consisting of 3 to 4 members.

The below figure indicates the six modeling indicators for employability, based on which five different types of students were classified.

	Modeling Indicators of Employability					
	Quality & Leadership	Initiative and Reaching Consensus	Idea Formulation	Understanding & Focus	Group Participation	General Knowledge
Type 1	X	X	X	X	X	X
Type 2		X	X	X	X	X
Type 3			X	X	X	X

Type 4				X	X	X
Type 5					X	X

Figure 3: Employability Indicators

Based on the above, we performed six to seven iterations over a period of two months with an average of over 100 students per iteration (the hiring interview process) covering 600 to 700 students who were in graduating class and eligible to get employed based on their completion of masters /bachelors degree requirements set by Srinivas University. The below figure 4 shows the data obtained on which we categorized the type of students. The data shown in figure is the average number of students per iteration i.e. the hiring process which had 5 scrutiny steps and lasted for around 4 to 5 hrs per iteration.(the hiring process was 4 to 5 hours)

Scrutiny	Total	Scrutiny 1 (Written Test)	Scrutiny 2 (GD 1)	Scrutiny 3 (GD 2)	Scrutiny 4 (GD 3)	Scrutiny 5 (Personal Interview)	Final
Student Type	100	20					
Type 5		80	30				10
Type 4			50	20			0
Type 3				30	20		15
Type 2					10	5	5
Type 1						5	5

Figure 4 : Types of Career Path

Type 1 students were exceptional and ready to be placed immediately, as they possessed the traits of quality leadership such as accountability, focus on innovative ideas, managing situations according to needs etc. Hence they were better in management aptitude, possessing effective listening, writing reasoning skills and were ready for managerial careers

Type 2 students were very good and possessed traits that include good verbal and nonverbal communication skills, maintaining relationships with their leaders as these were the students who had nominated Type 1 students for the final interview and hence can be efficient subordinates to Type 1, thereby being in role of efficient supervisors and project leaders

Type 3 students' traits include ability to work hard , but may need support from someone higher like Type 1 or Type 2 in case they are hired in the same organization or someone high in order/senior management within the hiring organization for other skills/hobby based Extracurricular which they possess and hence can contribute to the organization's overall welfare. They can perform very well in team lead as well as coordination based roles.

Among the other students who were unable to cross scrutiny 4, Type 5 students and Type 4 students cannot be employed due to certain reasons and may have to go through some forms of training to get employed. Finally the evaluation team felt that Type 5 students may possess all abilities, yet cannot be employed for family/business reasons, like wanting to have their own startups, as they were hesitant in participating further in the scrutiny despite possessing traits for employability. Hence they may be effective in consulting or being in business development executive roles in organizations that they may aspire to work for.

6. Conclusions.

All the Students who were scrutinized based on S.T.E.M integrated thought in the final round of interview were found to be very good than their counterparts in understanding their roles and can be molded on the lines of vision, mission, values of the organization in which they are found to be suitable. Henceforth, they would tend to have a better sustainability both in their career path as well

as their family lives in an age where artificial intelligence can aid them in bettering their employability thereby contributing towards both their organizations as well as to nation's vision, mission and thereby solving problems faced by Skills Acquisition and Knowledge Awareness for Livelihood Promotion(SANKALP) set by the Ministry of skill development and Entrepreneurship.

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